

IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING MICROBIOLOGY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY IN BIOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832316>

Annotation. *Science education plays an important role in the preparation of students in any educational system, because in the 21st century, scientific literacy has become a necessity for equal opportunities for all people. The subjects they include are responsible for developing the necessary skills for responsible interaction with the environment that surrounds all people living on our planet. Microbiology is the study of microorganisms, their biology and ecology. Today, microbiology is a specialized and precise science that has become indispensable to industry and the quality of our lives over time. The main goal of this article is to determine the place of microbiology science in environmental protection and conservation.*

Keywords: *education, microbiology, biotechnology, biotechnological education, industrial microbiology, current problems in teaching modern microbiology, solutions.*

Introduction

From ancient times to the Renaissance, science consists of contemplative knowledge of nature. One can get to the essence of nature through observation and meditation.

Science education plays an important role in the preparation of students in any educational system, because in the 21st century, scientific literacy has become a necessity for equal opportunities for all people. In turn, UNESCO declared in 1998 the importance of teaching them as a means of encouraging and developing critical thinking that allows them to solve various problems in different fields. On the other hand, the subjects they include are responsible for forming the necessary skills for a responsible relationship with the environment that surrounds all individuals living on our planet. Thus, teaching science involves many problems, such as the continuous description of only phenomena and experiences that preserve traditional pedagogy. However, when teaching is seen as a problematic situation, when it can stimulate students' scientific interest, engage them in their interests, challenge their everyday lives and tacit assumptions that are taken for granted or unquestionable, then progress in the field can be made. That is, you will encounter new models that play an important role in learning and teaching, challenging the integration of robust and innovative ideas. [1]

Knowledge of microbiology belongs to the natural sciences, and this type of scientific knowledge is knowledge that requires justification and proof through experience. Because this science requires methods and methods of substantiating the results obtained. In microbiology and biotechnology, scientific theories are derived from the results of experiments, and this method of presenting the results of science is called its systematic nature. The nature of explanation based on experience and practical knowledge means that the occurrence of a phenomenon can be explained through deductive procedures based on well-founded and proven science or scientific laws and a set of data. So, it can be said that explanation, that is, the feature of describing a process through scientific facts, implies systematization and the description of this process based on the obtained result. [3,4]

Microbiology is the study of microorganisms, their biology and ecology. Today, microbiology is a specialized and precise science that has become indispensable to industry and the quality of our lives over time. It should be noted that this science has found its place in various disciplines: molecular genetics, environment, physiology, medicine, food and metabolic and biochemistry. Undoubtedly, microbiology and microorganisms are central to the fundamental aspects of our society. Therefore, the main goal of this article is to explain the teaching of microbiology, which includes many fields such as industry and agriculture, with modern methods and teaching students using different methods and methods. The science of biotechnology is based on the life processes of microorganisms, and in this science, processes such as the synthesis of enzyme preparations, antibiotics, amino acids, hormones, protein substances and metabolites necessary for various branches of the national economy are explained with the help of examples. [2]

Importance of microbiology as a science in life. From an evolutionary point of view, biological changes in nature have created both challenges and opportunities for life forms: the challenge of adapting to new conditions and survival, and the possibility of occupying the natural space left by those who are unable to do so is strong, subject to any environment and external factors. was given to microorganisms that can adapt and have high tolerance properties. The science of microbiology and biotechnology is certainly one of the main sciences for understanding the impact of changes in nature on humans, predicting and dealing with its consequences, and preventing global problems. In agricultural microbiology, aspects such as adaptation of microorganisms to environmental effects and changes or how to use all the possibilities of beneficial microorganisms to maintain effective agriculture in additional unfavorable conditions (moisture, temperature, external environmental factors) are of interest. and is attracting the attention of more and more scientists. All research in this discipline provides relevant biological information, as well as new biotechnological tools in the form of enzymatic activity relevant to the environment, and the description of microorganisms with beneficial properties such as plant growth acceleration or protection against stress.[1]

The study of microbiology is very important because microorganisms are part of our nature. Microorganisms have been useful to humans even before we knew they existed. The study of microorganisms and the knowledge about them have been applied in medical, industrial, economic and environmental fields. Knowledge of microorganisms served to prevent economic losses in the production of agricultural products, to know pathogenic microorganisms that damage and harm crops. Also, the science of microbiology, in turn, allows the creation of biotechnological vaccines, with the help of which people and animals are protected from certain microorganisms and thereby prevent the transmission of diseases caused by them. From the point of view of industrial microbiology, we can present to use microorganisms and the metabolites they produce, even if they are produced on a large scale. For example, in the production of beer, wine and industrial products such as yeast, kefir and cheese.[3]

Currently, the production of biopolymers produced by microorganisms, similar in strength to synthetic polymers, but completely biodegradable, is being studied. We must mention the importance of microorganisms from an environmental point of view. These are the natural degradation of wastes and compounds that produce non-toxic compounds that are easily absorbed

by plants and other animals. However, due to the huge industrial activity and the current human lifestyle, as well as the population of the whole world, the amount and variety of natural and xenobiotic and often toxic wastes have far exceeded the production capacity. microorganisms to convert them naturally. This has led to the accumulation of these compounds in aquifers and soils and thus the imbalance of ecosystems, and many of these compounds have become toxic and have a greater impact on the lives of organisms that thrive in them. ecosystems. Ways to destroy or decompose these compounds from the environment through chemical, physical and biological processes were studied. The biological role of microorganisms is important because, thanks to their metabolism and/or enzymatic systems, they have the ability to convert, decompose, and at best mineralize CO₂, N₂, and H₂O into their simplest form. [2]

Pedagogical aspects of biological education and microbiology. Educational processes that include the teaching of biological education are aimed at increasing the awareness of individuals and society. In the same way, education forms a process that allows a person and society to know the world and reality, to interpret and explain them, to fully develop the ability to live in their own conditions. Biological education promotes development and increases the development potential of the population. Biological education is a driving force for changing people's attitudes so that they are able to appreciate and solve the problems of sustainable or alternative development. Biological education is aimed at developing the attitudes, abilities and skills necessary to understand and appreciate the interactions between humans and microorganisms, their characteristics and the processes that interact with the environment. It is a process that serves to satisfy needs, recognizes human values, and clarifies and enriches concepts. It recognizes the importance of education for the acquisition of biological and ethical, scientific consciousness, values, methods, techniques and behavior in accordance with sustainable development and ensures effective public participation in decision-making. [3]

Education promotes the value and necessity of local, national and international cooperation in solving human problems through microorganisms. Knowing the impact of biological education on the development of human society and the important support of higher education, we introduce this content to the science of microbiology. necessary, so that our students will be sure that industry and science can be further developed and developed through the science of microbiology and biotechnology in our country. The teaching of microbiology and biotechnology is based on theory and practice, in which the student develops conceptual, procedural and attitude skills. The main thing in teaching and learning this subject is not to give students correct or absolute knowledge, but to promote learning situations in which they are able to contrast and analyze different models. and it is assumed that apart from promotion. Curriculum always represents a cultural selection in the form of knowledge, skills, habits, beliefs and value systems, structured in such a way that, when mastered by the student, his/her own goals are achieved in the instructive and educational dimension. [2]

That is why we consider it important to include the following content through problem-based teaching methods:

- introduction to brief aspects of basic microbiology;
- review of some aspects of human health, starting from epidemiological giving insights about the processes up to the point of view;

- explain the aspects of microbiology applied in agriculture and industry;
- teaching the importance of basic microbiological and biotechnological processes and production through them;
- providing knowledge about the basics and stages of designing biological processes;
- to consider various philosophical theories that collect the historical foundations of human relations with the planet and its environment since ancient times, to explain and respond to the biological cycle. [4]

As a way to develop creative thinking in students through problem-based teaching in the study of microbiology and biotechnology with modern methods, focusing on its opposite sides, new relationships between reproductive and creative mastering of new content. It is important to learn knowledge such as installation. The formation of a problem situation goes through successive stages such as motivation, recognition, search, confrontation, application and creation. These methods and methods guide students in solving problems that are new to them, create a strategy that forces them to acquire knowledge independently, and encourage them to start new research on how to prevent this problematic situation, and thereby motivate students to further increase their interest in science.

Conclusion:

The teaching of microbiology is a reference point for the study of natural sciences due to its relevance, constant discovery, and diverse applications in various aspects of society. A number of global problems, such as the constant deterioration of nature and environment, the lack of products produced in industry, and the supply of human resources and food, encourage us to search for acceptable and sustainable scientific alternatives at the world level. As the main protagonist of the educational and scientific process, it is very important that we form the knowledge and values necessary to confront the biological crisis.

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